

Deliverable 4.3 Data Collating Plan

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1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims at a high-quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are targeted by DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report is relevant for the integration of knowledge and actions of all three stakeholders' groups. It contains a **Data collating plan** which documents the choices made to allow collating data from different data sources.

This data collating plan feeds into the broader objectives of task 4.2 which is: *Evaluating and selecting open access data sources useful for farmers, actors in the value chains and policy makers and to inform farm management and policy and investment decisions related to soil, land health, climate, biodiversity and sustainable farming.*

The aim is to create a central space where relevant data on agroforestry can easily be found and accessed, through permanent links. The Tools and data catalogue is available on the DigitAF website: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-and-data-catalogue/> and will be updated and populated with more datasets until the end of the project and beyond. The Data Catalogue will include: 1) regional agroforestry data with data on agroforestry systems, practices, tree and crop species; 2) data applicable on a wider scale, for instance spatial and biophysical databases containing data on e.g. land cover, soil, climate, erosion, wetness, or nutrient loads, 3) a catalogue of agroforestry-related projects (see image on first page). The DigitAF Data Catalogue is the result of a collaboration across multiple work packages. Early 2023, DigitAF project partners made a first inventory of potentially interesting datasets relevant for agroforestry. This inventory listed 71 data source topics or real existing datasets which would be important for the living labs involved in the project or for completing a specific project task. Hereafter, datasets have been added to complete ongoing project work focusing on e.g. agri-environmental indices (Kay et al. 2024) and Trees Outside Forests (WP1). In addition, datasets related to biodiversity, greenhouse gas emissions, carbon and soil health (WP3) have been added to the catalogue. Identifying datasets and making the data open access by uploading to the DigitAF Data Catalogue will continue until the end of the project in collaboration with all project partners, living lab leaders and members, tool developers and a wider community of interest (researchers, farm advisors, farmers).

2 Making agroforestry data accessible

There is a wealth of excellent information available on agroforestry. This information is captured in numerous scientific publications and technical reports. In addition, lots of useful information on

agroforestry is stored in databases containing data on land use, climate, weather, soil, crop yields, suitable tree species, agroforestry, agroforestry product information, biodiversity, ecosystem services, and so on. All this information would be useful for farmers who should decide on the best way how to manage their farm, for farm advisors who should provide solid advice to their customers, for researchers embarking on a new study related to agroforestry systems, for students working on their assignments, or for policy makers deciding on agricultural policies affecting all of us. However, information on agroforestry systems is currently scattered and there does not exist a clear entry point where all this valuable information produced by science and practice can be easily accessed (Tranchina et al. 2024). There are several past and ongoing initiatives to improve the access to information on agroforestry. For instance, the project [AFINET](#) (Agroforestry Innovation Networks) pooled knowledge created by earlier projects and initiatives by creating a Knowledge Cloud to make practical and scientific information with relevance for practical agroforestry management better available. The initiative started under AFINET now continues under a new project called [AF4EU](#) (Agroforestry Business Model Innovation Network) which has a more specific focus on developing innovative agroforestry business models. The [REFOREST](#) project aims at developing a knowledge exchange hub based on a specialized agricultural social network with the aim of leveraging the power of AKIS and other knowledge networks in upscaling agroforestry. The DigitAF project is focussed on facilitating the use of the wealth of available digital resources which could help in making the implementation of agroforestry into practice easier as well as informing extension work and agricultural policies. Its focus is on interoperability of data and tools, and applying the FAIR principles (see also section 3.1 on FAIR principles). The aim of the DigitAF Data Catalogue is to provide an easy to find and accessible entry point, where the most relevant data related to a broad spectrum of agroforestry topics can be found. This data repository is part of the Agroforestry Digital Space to engage all agroforestry stakeholders. The Agroforestry Digital Space currently contains a development platform on GitHub (<https://github.com/euraf>) for tool developers and a platform containing a Tools and Data Catalogue (<https://digitaf.eu/tools-and-data-catalogue/>) for all agroforestry stakeholders who are searching for data, interested in using a certain tools and/or adapting tools to their context.

3 The Data Catalogue

The main aim of the DigitAF Data Catalogue is to enhance the use of digital data to support decision making, planning and management of agroforestry systems. This will first be tested in the six living labs involved in the project, and during a later phase of the project we will involve a wider group of stakeholders. The Data Catalogue will help Living Labs in identifying useful and available datasets for its members, as well as creating a legacy after the project, where relevant datasets containing information relevant for agroforestry can be found and updated, and more data sources can be added. The aim is that the catalogue will reach a mostly self-sustained phase towards the end of the project as its users can take part in keeping datasets and the catalogue updated while EURAF will take care of essential maintenance and moderation. Thus, the main aim of the DigitAF Data Catalogue is not to create a new repository but its added value is mainly in facilitating data use through demonstrating and testing the usefulness of digital data with practitioners, advisors, researchers and policy stakeholders in living labs. Another aim of the Data Catalogue is to encourage data owners to make their data better available through applying the FAIR principles which help to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of digital resources (Tomás et al. 2024, and see also section 3.1 for a more detailed information on the FAIR principles).

The DigitAF data repository will not provide storage space for data. Instead, it is an entry point that links to published datasets which are stored on trusted and existing repositories. We are not going to copy and transfer data files to the DigitAF repository, and each dataset will remain in its original location.

How to retrieve data

The online Data Catalogue is available from the DigitAF project website at: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-and-data-catalogue/> (Figure 1). The Data Catalogue contains data relevant for agroforestry in the projects' six living labs but also more general data on temperate agroforestry. The focus is mainly on Europe, but it is not limited to Europe as some datasets are also relevant outside Europe or have a global scope.

The search box allows users to explore the datasets by entering a word from the title of the dataset (if known), a word in the description, or a keyword search. By using filters, users can explore the datasets by selecting different criteria such as the license of the dataset, the time interval in which the data were collected (e.g. second, minute, month, year), indicators or variables included in the data, regional extent (region, country, continent), spatial scale (from leaf to global), or type of data (e.g. experimental data, observational data, survey data, spatial data, etc.).

3.1 Fairness score

The "FAIRness score" concept is based on the FAIR principles (<https://www.go-fair.org>) which helps to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of digital resources. Each dataset will be scored according to these FAIR principles, using a FAIRness scoring tool developed within the DigitAF project. This scoring serves two objectives: i) to allow data and tool **producers** to self-assess their tool and to use the score decomposition as guides on which aspect of their data they could further improve to increase FAIRness, and ii) to allow data and tool **users** to find resources that they will easily find, access, connect with data they already use, and reuse. The DigitAF project has developed separate fairness scores for tools and for data (Tomás et al. 2024). These two fairness scoring systems follow the same principles, but they are slightly different from each other, because of the inherent difference that exists between data and tools. Data is basically just information such as facts and numbers. Digital tools are more complicated and can be defined as programs, websites, applications, and other internet and computerized resources that facilitate, enhance and execute digital processes. See Deliverable 4.5 by Tomás et al. (2024) for a more detailed description of the fairness score for tools and data.

3.2 Who can contribute?

Data generated or curated during the project could be useful to a range of stakeholders: first, to the three actor groups involved in the living labs (policy actors, practitioners, beneficiaries of agroforestry products and services), but also to researchers and students. It is expected that in the initial phase after launching the catalogue all project partners (living lab leaders, DigitAF task leaders and partners, tool developers) will populate the DigitAF data catalogue with data relevant for agroforestry. Towards, the later phase of the project, the intention is that any user may contribute with new datasets to the Data Catalogue, edit any incomplete or outdated information about any of the datasets, and that the interaction with the database and results display should be easy and comprehensible.

3.3 How to contribute

In DigitAF, the aim is not to reinvent the wheel and create a new data repository. Instead, the aim is to improve the access and findability of data, and how different datasets and models can “talk” to each other (Interoperability). Therefore, each dataset stays in its own original place. Our aim is only to enhance digital access and the use of digital resources. Therefore, before listing a dataset in the DigitAF Data Catalogue, each dataset should be published in an existing and trusted repository. There exist many data repositories and before adding a new dataset to the catalogue, it should be checked that the dataset is stored in a trusted repository preferably with a permanent link. Repositories owned and maintained by established and respected institutes and organisations are usually a safe choice. Examples of repositories are:

- Public open access repositories, e.g. zenodo, openaire, github
- Global datasets repositories (e.g. NASA, ESA, CIFOR-ICRAF, FAO).
- European data repositories (e.g. Copernicus, LUCAS, etc).
- Statistical databases (FADN, Eurostat, national statistics)
- University and institutional repositories

If the dataset of your interest is already published in an existing repository, you can start uploading it directly to the Data Catalogue (Figure 1). During the uploading process you need to complete all the required metadata. Therefore, it is recommended to explore the dataset of your interest and familiarize yourself with its content.

There will be a quality assurance step after adding new dataset entries, assuring that the minimum information is correctly provided.

For now uploading data is done mainly by the living labs. This is still part of a testing phase where we gather feedback and gradually make improvements. Uploading data to the catalogue is done manually by filling in the form.

Later on during the project we will explore how harvesting and updating metadata of datasets can be done automatically. This feature of the catalogue is still under development. Automatic harvesting and updating metadata of linked datasets is possible for instance with some of the tools and methods developed by the Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) or using an API (Application Programming Interface) via the data link.

For those datasets where automatic harvesting is possible, no form needs to be completed. The form needs to be completed in case automatic harvesting is not possible, or in case automatically harvested metadata is incomplete.

Tools and Data Catalogue

Agroforestry Data Catalogue

Do a self-assessment of the FAIRness of your dataset [here](#).

SEARCH:

search in *name*
 search in *description*
 search in *keywords*

LICENSE

Search

MIT License (0)
 Apache License 2.0 (0)
 GNU General Public License (GPL) (0)
 Creative Commons BY (5)
 Creative Commons BY-SA (0)

Displaying 24 datasets

HAZEL.trial.ILVO

Keywords
Silvopastoral, Variety trial, Hazelnut, Nut production

FAIRness score

F	67%
A	75%
I	10%
R	50%

In 2017, 168 hazel trees (*Corylus avellana* cvs.) of eight different varieties, were planted in a randomized design on an experimental plot at ILVO (coordinates: 50.976816, 3.778914). The eight cultivars selected were 'Emoa 1', 'Hall's Giant', 'Corabel', 'Gunslebert', 'Kentish cob', 'Gustav's Zeller', 'Cosford' and 'Tonda di Giffoni'. They were planted in such a way that each cultivar was represent...

ESA Worldcover 2021

Keywords
Spatial, Groundcover

This dataset contains spatial data about groundcover classes, based on a last update in 2021. The product map is viewable and downloadable on a 10m resolution. It is a fast generation and validation of a world land cover

Figure 1. Example of a dataset available from the Data Catalogue. You can add a new dataset by pressing the button "Add a new dataset"

If the dataset that you would like to contribute to the Data Catalogue is not published, you first need to publish it. Unpublished data can be made public, for example in Zenodo (Figure 2). In the following sections we will explain how to publish a dataset in Zenodo.

Figure 2. Published datasets can be uploaded straight to the DIGITAF Data Catalogue. Previously unpublished data should first be uploaded to an existing repository, before adding it to the Data Catalogue. Zenodo is an example of an existing repository.

3.4 Publishing unpublished datasets

Some living lab members or stakeholders possibly possess potentially valuable and so far unpublished data collected during the DigitAF project or other projects. If Living Lab stakeholders wish to make these data available on the DigitAF repository, the data should first be published. Data can be published in an institutional repository, or, in case no institutional repository is available, Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) would be a suitable option. Publishing data on Zenodo is possible via the stakeholder's own Zenodo account, or in case the stakeholder does not have an own account and is not willing to create one (it is however super easy), it can be the account of the Living Lab leader. You can create a Zenodo account here: <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/get-started/create-an-account/>

3.5 Publishing data on Zenodo

When uploading datasets to Zenodo, they need to be collated with the necessary metadata as required by Zenodo. It is not enough to just upload a dataset but sufficient metadata needs to be added such as: title, authors, description of the data. If available, it would be good to add as much detailed information as possible for example a report or (a link to an) article containing information related to the dataset. A brief report with at least the following points would be good to add: Introduction (stating in particular the context and the aim of data collection), methods (e.g. study design, experimental setup, data collection), results, discussion of the results.

When uploading a dataset to Zenodo you will be asked which license to use. If you haven't decided yet which license to use, it does not matter what you use, you can change it later, by clicking on "edit here" and submitting the changes.

Datasets uploaded to Zenodo via your own account can be added to the [EURAF community on Zenodo](#). This would increase visibility of previously unpublished datasets relevant for agroforestry in Europe made available during the DigitAF project.

The documentation in Zenodo is very good and usually there are no major problems adding a dataset or a publication. If you run into trouble, the Zenodo help function will provide most of the answers (<https://help.zenodo.org/>) so no need to repeat them here.

4 Metadata for datasets on the DigitAF Data Catalogue

In the early phase after launching the catalogue, datasets need to be collated manually by filling in the form. In a later phase we will explore possibilities for automatic adding and updating metadata (section 3.3).

To collate the datasets, for each dataset the following meta-data needs to be completed when listing a new dataset in the Data Catalogue (Table 1). The form for adding a new dataset is accessible here: <https://digitaf.eu/tools-and-data-catalogue/> by pressing the button "Add a new dataset".

Table 1. Required metadata to collate datasets when uploading to the Data Catalogue. [F, A, I, R] between brackets refer to questions for evaluating the Fairness score.

Question / required metadata to collate the dataset	Type of answer / possible answers
Name of the responsible for entering this data	Name: Character string (free text)
Email of the responsible for entering this data	E-mail address: Character string (free text)
Name of the dataset	Character string (free text)
What is the link to the dataset?	URL
Is the link to the dataset a unique and persistent identifier? [F1]	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Yes• No
Dataset description	Character string (free text)
Keywords	Character string (free text)
Who, or which organization, is the data owner?	Character string (free text)

Question / required metadata to collate the dataset	Type of answer / possible answers
Provide some contact information regarding the dataset.	Character string (free text)
Was the data collected during a project?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No, it has another source • Don't know
If yes, what was the name of the project?	Character string (free text)
If yes, please provide a project URL (preferably of CORDIS if available)	URL
Regional extent, e.g. country (or region) where the data was collected?	<p>The country name: Character string (free text)</p> <p>During the initial phase, only living labs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Belgium • Czech republic • Finland • France • Germany • Italy • Netherlands • United Kingdom • Europe • Global • Other
Type of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregated data • Analysis data • Audiovisual corpus • Computer code • Experimental data • Observational data • Simulation data • Spatial data • Survey data • Text corpus • Other
What's the spatial scale of the data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leaf/stem (sub-individual) • Plant/animal • Plot • One-hectare • Farm • Landscape • Catchment • Ecosystem Service Spatial Unit (ESSU) • Regional • National • European • Global • Other
If applicable, give further spatial details (e.g. resolution, grid size)	Character string (free text)
What indicators are included in the dataset?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth • Yield / Biomass • Biodiversity • Species occurrence

Question / required metadata to collate the dataset	Type of answer / possible answers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land cover • Land use • Vegetation indexes • Phenology • Suitability • Water • Meteorology • Soil • Carbon • Nutrients • Mechanization • Labour • Social • Economics • Nutrition • Animal welfare • Mortality • Pests and Diseases • Other
At which time intervals is the data collected?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hourly • Daily • Weekly • Fortnightly • Monthly • Yearly • Not relevant • Other
What was the year of release?	YEAR
What year was it last updated?	YEAR
Time span covered by the database: year of oldest observation	YEAR
Time span covered by the database: year of newest observation	YEAR
Is the data confidential?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No, the data is public • Yes, it is confidential data • Data embargo, i.e there are rules or limits on using, sharing, or spreading it • Data has a limiting license
What is the usage rights license for the dataset?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MIT License • Apache License 2.0 • GNU General Public License (GPL) • Creative Commons BY • Creative Commons BY-SA • Creative Commons BY-NC • Creative Commons BY-NC-SA • Creative Commons BY-ND • Creative Commons BY-NC-ND • Creative Commons Zero (CC0) • Proprietary • Not stated • Don't know • Other

Question / required metadata to collate the dataset	Type of answer / possible answers
Please indicate the URL to the license.	URL
Is there any barrier to accessing the data? [A1]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No, direct download/access through a web link • User registration needed • Access to the data needs to be granted (e.g. dataset owner needs to give permission after user registration; dataset owner sends data after receiving a request email) • Access to the data is evaluated before being granted, due to ethical, legal or contractual constraints (e.g. privacy, highly sensitive data)
What is the format of the data? [I1]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Widely used file formats (Spreadsheet, JSON, GeoJSON, SHP, GPX, KML, XML, TIFF, MP3, MP4, etc.) • Custom file formats (database specific, not widely used) • Static content (e.g. textual, reports on website pages, tables and graphs, PDF files) • Other
The data (or its metadata) is accurate and well described with many relevant attributes? [R1]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • Not completely • No • Don't know
Is the dataset also listed in other databases? [F3]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Don't know
If applicable and known, in which databases is it listed?	Character string (free text)
The dataset has an associated metadata file (e.g. XML, md), where the dataset details are described? [F2]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Don't know
Is the metadata file, or documentation, fully accessible, even if the data may not be publicly available? [A2]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • Some of it • No • Don't know
Does the metadata file, or documentation, follow any controlled vocabularies, keywords, thesauri or ontologies? [I2]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No • Don't know
It is clear how, why and by whom the data have been created and processed? [R3]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • Not completely • No • Don't know
Indicate the associated publication(s) or other documentation related with the dataset.	Character string (free text)
For DigitAF participants, in which DigitAF Living Labs is the data being used?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Czech Republic LL • Finland LL • Germany LL • Italy LL • Netherlands LL • United Kingdom LL
For DigitAF participants, in what WPs is this data being used?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1 - Tools for policy-makers • WP2 - Tools for practitioners and farm advisors • WP3 - Tools for beneficiaries

Question / required metadata to collate the dataset	Type of answer / possible answers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP4 - LL and a common AF toolbox
For DigitAF participants, please detail how is this data being used within the project context.	Character string (free text)
Is there any relevant information about the dataset that hasn't been collected in the previous questions?	Character string (free text)

In case new data fields are added to the data collating plan, these should be in line with existing ontologies such as e.g. AGROVOC (FAO, 2022) for the commonly used concepts in agriculture, AOBRA (Conde-Salazar et al. 2021) which is more specifically for agroforestry, or the BONARES metadata scheme (Gärtner et al. 2017) for spatial data. Linkage with the existing agroforestry and other ontologies is still under development. Linkage with existing ontologies will limit complexity and will allow integration of existing and new data in an organised knowledge base (Stokes et al. 2023).

Ontologies are useful for providing an overview of the knowledge available in a field, for instance agricultural science. There exists masses of data such as field observations, documents and visual supports, collected by different stakeholders such as biologists, foresters, farmers and breeders, but the management and reuse of these data are made difficult by the multiplicity of media and formats used, and by the diversity of vocabularies (Stokes et al. 2023). An ontology formally describes the concepts used in a field of knowledge, and makes it possible to add new concepts to this description.

4.1 Metadata for Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) data

The Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) is a geographic information system used to support the management and control of agricultural subsidies within the European Union. It plays a crucial role in the administration of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), which aims to provide financial support to farmers, promote sustainable agriculture and guarantee food security (European Court of Auditors 2019). LPIS uses geospatial data to identify and map agricultural parcels. This includes information on the boundaries, size, and location of each parcel of land. LPIS maintains a comprehensive database of all agricultural land parcels within a European member state, including detailed attributes of each parcel, for instance the type of crops or land use (arable, pasture, permanent crop). It contains many features which are relevant for the assessments and tools developed in DigitAF, for example it is used in WP1 for assessing Trees Outside Forests, and in WP 1/3 for the Open Farm Carbon Tracker (OFCT).

Therefore, LPIS data will have its own section in the Data Catalogue. Indeed, in order for tools relying on LPIS to work reliably, it is necessary to ensure permanent availability, which is often not the case when trying to retrieve data from national data service providers or even from the DGAGRI attempt at creating an inventory of [Member State Geoportals](#) (including some IACS data). In addition, even though the data structure is more or less similar for most countries, this data is not harmonised and there are differences in crop names and crop codes, or information on eligibility of parcels. Furthermore, not all data is publicly available in all countries. Therefore it is useful to see in a centralized way which data is available for the different countries, and what is their metadata. Potentially, the data catalogue could be used to develop a unique entry point for all LPIS systems for agroforesters, allowing streamlining of data handling pipelines for any application relying on LPIS. It would be totally open source allowing to contribute to recurring updates.

LPIS data has been gathered for all European countries for which it was available (LPIS data is publicly available for all EU countries except for Cyprus, some of the German Länder, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Malta, and Poland, where we have so far not been able to retrieve LPIS data). In addition, we retrieved

LPIS data for non-EU countries Norway, Switzerland and Iceland. Unlike the other datasets, for which we invited project partners, living lab members and other stakeholders to contribute new data sets, LPIS data will only be gathered and collated by researchers who are already familiar with this type of data. Collating LPIS data is still under development and therefore this plan may still see some changes. It will, however, follow the same logic as for the other datasets described in the previous section as much as possible. Nevertheless, there are many differences compared to the other data, for example information on indicators (e.g. crops and crop codes, land use, eligibility information of land parcels, etc). Therefore, we have developed a different metadata structure for collating LPIS data (Table 2).

Table 2. Required metadata to collate LPIS data for the Data Catalogue.

Main category	Question /required metadata	Type of answer / possible answers
	Country	Name of country
	Region	Name of region
	Name of LPIS dataset	Text
	Organization responsible for the LPIS	Text
	Landing page URL	URL
	Does the LPIS landing page have easily accessible information?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • Not completely • No • Don't know
	Viewer URL	URL
	Dataset URL (WMS/WFS, SHP, ...)	URL
	Name of the responsible for entering this data	Name
	Email of the responsible for entering this data	e-mail
Land Use	Land use details (URL Link, codes list, description)	URL, list of codes or description
	Crop codes details (URL link to codes list, description)	URL, list of codes or description
	Main land cover categories	Text
	Has agroforestry related land uses? Which ones?	Text
Access	LPIS data access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free access • Limited free access • Access available upon registration • Access available only upon request • No access (only for specific applicants)
	Cadastre layer available?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
Reference parcels		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No

Main category	Question /required metadata	Type of answer / possible answers
	Ortho-imagery last update	YEAR
	Available time-series	YEAR - YEAR
Eligibility percentage for Direct Payments	Calculation details	Text
	Publicly available?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
Trees outside Forests Type of geographical representation	Landscape Features layer publicly available?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Information on Landscape Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Information on Ecological Focus Areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Hedges or woody strips - Landscape Feature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Hedges or woody strips - Ecological Focus Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Buffer strips - Landscape Feature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Buffer strips - Ecological Focus Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Trees in line - Landscape Feature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Trees in line - Ecological Focus Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Trees in groups / Copses - Landscape Feature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Trees in groups / Copses - Ecological Focus Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Isolated trees - Landscape Feature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
	Isolated trees - Ecological Focus Area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
		Relevant notes or comments

As with other datasets, in the case where new data fields are added to the data collating plan, these will follow terminology used in existing ontologies or the BONARES Metadata Scheme for spatial data (Gärtner et al. 2017) as much as possible to make interoperability between data catalogues easier. In order to avoid errors in applications relying on the data, two options are possible. The first one is ensuring that the “live” links are still working by creating a checker function to automatically and regularly "pings" all links that are present in the database and list the "404 results". The output would be those errors, together with the github file to edit and suggest a pull request or create an issue to the github AF catalogue project. The second option is to setup permanent DOIs with raw data instead of using national data end-points, which from our own experience break very often. The advantage of this solution is that the data can be pre-processed to generate a harmonized version of the individual datasets, translated to a shared English format, with common land use/crop codes, derived variables (such as polygon area and boundary perimeter) without missing values, etc... This would also allow

for the best performance in a web environment where we want to have seamless cross border data coverage, by choosing a set-up that would be specifically adapted to the agroforestry tools into which we want to feed the data. The downside would be that the data would not be automatically kept up to date, but would need periodic (e.g. annually) updates. The solution that will be chosen depends on the type of data we include in the LPIS section of the data catalogue (links to data providers or storage of raw data itself), which is still under discussion.

5 Outlook and next steps

Many relevant datasets have already been added to the Data Catalogue and this will continue until the end of the project. The Data Catalogue will be used for demonstrating and testing the usefulness of available data to the living labs, and at a later stage also the wider agroforestry stakeholder community and policy. By doing this we hope to facilitate the use of digital data in decision making to advocate fact-based decision making based on data and solid information. Some of the data sets have already been used in completing ongoing project work focusing on agri-environmental indices (DigitAF Deliverable report 1.2 by Kay et al. 2024) and Trees Outside Forests (WP1) by Lawson et al. (*submitted*). In addition, datasets related to biodiversity, greenhouse gas emissions, carbon and soil health (WP3) have been added to the catalogue. Identifying datasets and making the data open access by uploading to the DigitAF Data Catalogue will continue until the end of the project in collaboration with all project partners, living lab leaders and members, tool developers and a wider community of interest (researchers, farm advisors, farmers).

Next steps:

1. **Add relevant data sources** (continuous process until June 2026): Living Labs and project partners continue adding relevant datasets.
2. **Integrate LPIS data** (December 2024): Finalise metadata structure, retrieve metadata, retrieve LPIS data from missing countries if possible, add to Data Catalogue).
3. **Automatic harvesting and updating metadata** (February 2025). Explore the use of OAI-PMH and API in harvesting metadata (see section 3.3).
4. **Link with existing ontologies** (April 2025). Explore how data interoperability can be improved by linking with existing ontologies and explore improvements to existing agroforestry ontology (see Chapter 4).
5. **Involve wider agroforestry community** (August 2025). Living Labs are using the Data Catalogue throughout the project. As soon as Living Labs start giving feedback that we have a system that works, we can start involving a wider agroforestry community (maybe starting with the sister projects).
6. **Self-maintained phase (January - June 2026 and beyond)**: The community of users can add, update and remove datasets by themselves. Also quality checks can be done by the community. EURAF takes care of moderation and essential maintenance that cannot be done by the community.

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